

Netnography of Sustainable Tourism in the Triangle of Skills, Values and Outcomes

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Abstract

The Social Studies Curriculum (SSC) aims to equip individuals with certain attitudes, values, and skills to address the environmental, economic, and social issues, which are the core elements of sustainability. In this regard, the purpose of this study is to reveal the extent to which the intended outcomes have been achieved in society through social studies education, which aims to develop the skills and values necessary to understand sustainability in tourism. This research was conducted using a qualitative research method and designed as a case study. The BlaBla-Car application was selected as the case study of the research. The data obtained from SSC and Sikayetvar.com through document review and netnography methods were analyzed using document analysis, content analysis, and descriptive analysis. The findings indicate that all the values and skills included in the SSC contribute to the understanding of sustainability in tourism. Similarly, it was found that nearly one-third of the learning outcomes in the program

aim to contribute to the development of tourism and the understanding of sustainability in tourism. However, the findings derived from the case study demonstrate that individuals hinder economic sustainability in tourism by exploiting legal loopholes and engaging in illicit activities. Furthermore, individuals are driving society toward a socio-culturally unsustainable state by engaging in actions such as harassment, deceit, and distrust. In this context, it can be argued that the values, skills, and outcomes theoretically conveyed through SSC are not sufficiently reflected in practice, rendering the program ineffective.

Keywords: Tourism Education, Sustainable Tourism, Social Studies, Social Studies Curriculum, Sharing Economy.

JEL Codes: L83, Q01, Q56, I25, Z32

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Introduction

Since the Industrial Revolution, humanity has been engaged in a struggle with nature over the use of limited resources (Malik et al., 2024). When this struggle began to threaten the future, education emerged as a widely recognized solution (Pinto & Nakatani, 2022) as the ability of individuals to live without causing harm to each other or the environment can only be gained through education (Turan, 2019). In this regard, societies guide individuals toward the ideal order through various subjects taught in schools. Among the subjects that play a key role in shaping society is Social Studies. Social Studies first emerged in the United States (Sevigen, 2021) and aims to raise individuals as active and responsible citizens (Sevigen, Acun, & Üztemur, 2022). In Türkiye, this subject first appeared in the 1962 primary school curriculum under the title "Society and Country Studies" and was renamed "Social Studies" in 1968 (Öztürk, 2006).

Social studies focus on the ever-changing needs and dynamics of society, which leads to the inclusion of new areas, topics, and concepts in the scope of this course (İlhan, Şeker, & Kapıcı, 2015). One of the concepts emphasized in the SSC is tourism, which holds significant economic and cultural importance. The program implemented in 1968 adopted goals such as introducing tourism to students, explaining its importance, fostering tourism awareness, and raising awareness about tourism elements. In contrast, the 2018 curriculum placed greater emphasis on the importance of tourism in international relations (Yıldırım & Çetin, 2022). The "Global Connections" learning area in this program focuses mainly on tourism topics. This area is designed to equip students with knowledge and skills regarding economic interactions between regions, the role of technology and transportation in international economic relations, tourism, and international cooperation (Turan, 2019).

SSC plays an active role in instilling tourism awareness. İlhan et al. (2015) revealed that fifth-grade social studies textbooks introduce tourist destinations both visually and textually and provide information about attractions on the UNESCO World Heritage list. Kaya (2019) conducted a similar study and found that information and visuals related to tourism were sufficiently included in all levels of both the social studies program and social studies textbooks. Stating that the social studies course plays an important role in teaching cultural heritage subjects, Yalçın (2024) examined the materials of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism used in teaching them. Accordingly, it was found that the social studies course offers a wide range of materials for teaching cultural heritage topics, and that the use of these materials in classroom activities can produce effective results. Yıldırım and Çetin (2022) state that the curriculum that places the most emphasis on tourism

is the 1968 SSC, while the curriculum that gives it the least attention is the 2018 SSC. In their research, they concluded that, despite the increasing importance of tourism for countries, it is not adequately reflected in the curriculum. In terms of sustainable tourism, the conservation of environmental, social and cultural values also plays an important role in education (Yayla, 2020). In this context, Kaya and Tomal (2011) stated that since 2005, the SSC has aimed to equip individuals with the attitudes, values and skills necessary to tackle environmental, economic and social issues, which are essential for sustainable tourism.

Previous studies indicate that SSC aims to raise tourism awareness among individuals within the scope of cultural heritage, tourism, and the social, environmental, and economic impacts of tourism. However, a review of the literature revealed no research examining whether the values, skills, and outcomes theoretically conveyed in the social studies curriculum regarding tourism have been effectively implemented in practice. This indicates a significant gap in literature. In this context, the purpose of this study is to determine the extent to which the desired outcomes have been achieved through social studies education, which aims to impart the skills and values necessary for sustainable tourism. Accordingly, this research aims to answer the following questions:

1. Which learning outcomes in the SSC are related to tourism?
2. Which learning outcomes in the SSC are related to sustainable tourism?
3. To what extent do individuals possess the skills, values, and outcomes necessary for sustainable tourism?

A qualitative research approach was adopted to address the research questions. For the case study, the BlaBlaCar application was selected as the sample case. Founded in 2006 with the aim of bringing drivers and passengers together, BlaBlaCar (Talandier et al., 2024) is a sharing economy platform that has emerged in the tourism market in recent years (Skalska, 2017). The application, which offers affordable and flexible travel options, brings together more than 100 million drivers and passengers today. BlaBlaCar, a leading company in its field, is not only an online travel platform but also a cloud-based data storage service (Hanchuk et al. 2023). Given these effective functions as a travel application, BlaBlaCar offers a remarkable case study opportunity for tourism activities.

The study is significant not only for providing valuable insights into whether the social studies course is effective in shaping tourism behavior, but also for revealing the extent to which individuals possess the attitudes, values, and skills required for the environmental, social, and economic aspects of sustainability. Therefore, while contributing to filling the gap

in the literature on this topic, the study also offers suggestions for improving practical teaching methods in the social studies course to make students' attitudes, values, and skills more effective, beyond the theoretical aspects.

In line with the general framework presented above, a conceptual framework is first provided, explaining the relationship between the learning outcomes of the social studies curriculum and sustainable tourism. Subsequently, details regarding the research methodology are outlined, followed by a presentation of the findings obtained through this method. Finally, the research findings are discussed, leading to significant conclusions and the corresponding recommendations for the field are proposed.

Literature Review

The Role of Tourism in the Social Studies Curriculum

The social studies course, which covers many subjects concerning society, has two primary objectives in countries like the United States, Australia, and Canada: to develop the ability to understand global events and to foster citizenship awareness, thereby promoting active participation in societal life (Öztürk & Kafadar, 2020). Due to its multidisciplinary structure, the social studies course is capable of conducting studies across various fields (Üztemur, Sevigen & İnel, 2021). One of the disciplines included in the social studies course is tourism. While there is no course at the primary education level in Türkiye that directly teaches tourism, the only course that indirectly covers tourism topics is social studies. Although the SSC does not have a specific learning area dedicated to tourism, the subject is addressed across a broad spectrum of social sciences, including history, geography, economics, sociology, and culture. Among these learning areas, tourism is most prominently emphasized in the "Global Connections" section. According to Turan (2019), this learning area is designed to equip students with knowledge and skills in topics such as economic interactions between regions, the role of technology and transportation in international economic relations, tourism, and international cooperation.

Today, as states strive to develop their tourism industries in order to capture a larger share of the global tourism market, the importance of tourism education has become more apparent (Kaya, 2021). An examination of the curricula of the social studies course over time reveals that the relationship between the course and tourism fluctuates periodically. For example, in the 1968 curriculum, objectives such as introducing tourism to students, explaining its importance, fostering tourism awareness, and raising awareness about tourism elements were adopted. However, in the 1998 curriculum, due to the increased emphasis on development through national

resources and values, concepts related to tourism were given less prominence compared to the previous programs (Yıldırım & Çetin, 2022). The SSC currently in use in Türkiye was issued in 2018 (Turkish Ministry of National Education, 2018). In this curriculum, the concept of tourism is explicitly mentioned, and there is an important learning outcome that focuses on the significance of tourism in international relations (Yıldırım & Çetin, 2022).

Social studies education is also important at the global level, and many countries (such as the USA, England, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Sweden, Japan, Canada, Norway, Jamaica, Singapore, New Zealand, the Czech Republic, South Africa, and Egypt) have their own SSC. While each country tailors its curriculum based on its unique historical, geographical, and socio-cultural features, these programs aim to instill common behaviors in students. Numerous studies have been conducted in the literature on social studies curricula in different countries regarding this topic (Giroux & Penna, 1979; Arthur & Davison, 2000; Ross, 2006; Kuş, 2014; Jakubowski, 2023; Jamil, Aslam & Ali, 2024). There are also studies comparing the social studies curriculum of countries (Schwartz et al., 2012), focusing on values education (Schwartz, 1992; Schwartz et al., 2001; Thornberg & Oğuz, 2013), and examining these programs in terms of sustainability (Alelaimat & Taha, 2013).

The SSC in Turkey possesses an interdisciplinary framework designed to impart knowledge about social structure, cultural heritage, and economic activities. To demonstrate that social studies encompass more than just history, geography, and citizenship classes, it is essential to understand the foundational principles and the several disciplines that constitute this field (Keçe & Merey, 2011). The SSC encompasses each learning area that addresses fundamental issues of a particular scientific domain, supplemented by insights from other disciplines. Upon examining the relationship between many scientific disciplines and tourism within the SSC, it becomes evident that history and tourism are two interrelated fields that enhance one another. Individuals are provided the chance to engage with history through cultural tourism. This enables individuals to establish an emotional connection with the historical sites they explore (Metin, 2006). Similarly, the notion of heritage holds significant relevance in the realm of tourism geography within social studies curricula. The initial destinations accessible to tourists are often sites of natural and cultural heritage. Pamukkale-Hierapolis is referred to as "geographical heritage" because of its integration of tourism and geography (Doğaner, 2019). In the realm of citizenship education, tourism fosters environmental awareness by promoting individuals to become conscientious and responsible tourists. Consequently, in the context of the social studies curriculum, tourism is regarded not merely as an industry but also as an interdisciplinary field

that enhances individuals' awareness of the globe.

The Understanding of Sustainability in Social Studies Curriculum

Research on the inclusion of tourism in social studies education has identified several deficiencies arising from the curriculum, textbooks, or teachers. For example, İlhan, Şeker, and Kapıcı (2015) emphasized that the concept of tourism in social studies textbooks in Türkiye is often focused primarily on summer tourism. Keçe (2015), in a study conducted on prospective social studies teachers, found that while these groups had a positive attitude toward historical and cultural tourism values, they lacked sufficient knowledge on the subject. A review of the literature on the inclusion of tourism topics in social studies courses shows that cultural heritage and museology are commonly explored areas. (Danacı Polat, 2019; Aydoğan, 2020; Sevigen et al., 2022; Hündür, 2022; İnanlı, 2023). However, in the literature, no studies linking social studies curriculum to tourism areas focused on sustainable tourism or sustainability have been found. Yet, it is evident that increasing environmental awareness is one of the fundamental goals of the social studies course. In this context, one of the specific objectives of the course includes the statement: "Item 6: To recognize the limitations of natural resources and the environment, to strive to protect natural resources with environmental awareness, and to develop an understanding of a sustainable environment" (Turkish Ministry of National Education, 2018). In this regard, it was found that the social studies course aims to impart understanding and skills related to all dimensions of sustainable tourism—economic, socio-cultural, and environmental.

While the concept of sustainability, as taught in the social studies course, is crucial for all sectors of the tourism industry, it can be argued that it holds particular significance for the transportation sector. According to the World Tourism Organization's data for 2024, an estimated 1.4 billion tourists participated in international travel. In this respect, tourism contributes to over 5 percent of global greenhouse gas emissions (UNWTO, 2025), 90 percent of which comes from transportation (Kelly et al., 2007). Tourists can harm the environment by generating carbon emissions from the very beginning of their journey while traveling to their destination. As a result, going on vacation is not always an environmentally friendly activity (Dolnicar, 2020). Although the transportation sector is often associated with negative environmental impacts, it can also play a crucial role in economic sustainability. While economically sustainable transportation aims for a cost-effective transportation structure, it also takes into account factors such as economic activities, productivity, tax burden and employment (Nalçakan, Tutar, & Tutar, 2012). In this respect, the transportation sector can create direct

or indirect impacts in various economic areas such as reducing transportation costs, fostering integration in international trade, promoting economic growth, enhancing employment, improving productivity, and developing a competitive structure (Kara & Cığırlioğlu, 2018). The transportation sector can affect not only environmental and economic areas but also social sustainability. In this regard, social sustainability in transportation refers to meeting societal needs in an equitable manner. This includes justice, suitability for human health, and historical, cultural, and social relationships (Nalçakan, Tutar & Tutar, 2012). An effective transportation system brings regions closer together, fostering the blending of customs and traditions that reflect the identity of societies. As a result, structurally isolated communities can, through the transportation sector, shift away from traditional attitudes and behaviors, and evolve into more open and interactive societies (Ayaz & Bakan, 2022).

Another model that promotes sustainable development of tourism while enhancing social welfare and economic progress is the sharing economy. This model mitigates adverse effects on the environment and society while simultaneously lowering expenses (Perkumienė et al., 2021). This business model provided the foundation for the development of the BlaBlaCar application, which was designed to facilitate travel-related activities. BlaBlaCar is a ride-sharing network that connects drivers with available seats in their cars to passengers traveling in the same direction. This application helps address traffic problems both environmentally and economically without the need to introduce new vehicles to the transportation system (Cohen & Kietzmann, 2014). Additionally, the application offers social benefits for both drivers and passengers, such as getting to know each other and forming new friendships (Fitzmaurice et al., 2020). BlaBlaCar, which was established in 2006 with the aim of transforming idle vehicle capacity into a community-based travel network, has since grown into a \$2 billion platform operating in 22 countries (Yurdakul, Kiracı & Çetin, 2023). Moreover, BlaBlaCar, a prominent application in the tourism sector in recent years (Skalska, 2017), brings together over 100 million users worldwide (Hanchuk et al. 2023). Investigating the attitudes and behaviors of the user base of this platform which is claimed to have many social, environmental, and economic benefits, and its contribution to the understanding of sustainability can reveal the extent to which social studies education succeeds in shaping society. Thus, the BlaBlaCar application was chosen as the case study for this research.

Methodology

In this study, document analysis and netnography methods were utilized. Netnography is a modern qualitative research method that adapts ethnography

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hic research techniques to study cultures and communities that emerge through computer-mediated communication (Kozinets, 2002). While the netnography method has garnered increasing attention in interdisciplinary research in recent years (Tiryaki, 2023) and its use in the field of tourism is expanding (Tavakoli & Wijesinghe, 2019), its application in the field of education remains quite limited (Yavuz & Toprakçı, 2021). This method was chosen for its emphasis on online data and its effectiveness as a key tool for analyzing large datasets. This method was chosen for its focus on online data and its recognition as an effective tool for analyzing large datasets.

Research Design

This research adopts a qualitative research approach and is designed as a case study. A case study involves the detailed examination of a single case to explain broader phenomena (Davey, 2009). Case studies are a research design in which a current situation within defined boundaries in a certain period of time is described through in-depth data collection (Creswell 2013). The distinct feature of case studies, compared to other research methods, is their ability to explore, describe, and explain events believed to have causal relationships (Yin, 2009).

Population and Sample

The study population consists of complaints and reviews related to BlaBlaCar on the official sikayetvar.com website. BlaBlaCar, one of the world's largest online platforms (OECD, 2019), is a ride-sharing travel network founded in France in 2006, with over 90 million members across 22 countries (BlaBlaCar, 2024). The platform's goal is to reduce travel costs by connecting drivers and passengers traveling in the same direction, foster socialization and enjoyable journeys through mutual trust, and contribute to a sustainable environment by reducing CO² emissions (BlaBlaCar, 2024). Sikayetvar.com is an online complaint platform established in 2001 to serve as a bridge between consumers and brands, facilitating the resolution of consumer complaints. The platform, which influences consumers' purchasing decisions and brand preferences, receives approximately 14,000 real consumer complaints daily. These complaints are easily and freely communicated to brands through the platform, allowing brands to provide solutions to the issues raised (Sikayetvar.com, 2024). The reason for selecting the sikayetvar.com platform within the scope of this study is that it provides access to all complaints and reviews related to BlaBlaCar from a single online source. However, this also represents a limitation of the study. Although the platform offers comprehensive access to comments about BlaBlaCar, it is primarily used by individuals to submit complaints, as indicated by its name. As a result, the platform predominantly features negative

comments rather than positive ones. The sample for this study consists of all complaints and reviews submitted by BlaBlaCar users on this online platform.

Data Collection Process

In the first phase of the study, corresponding to the first two research questions, the SSC, most recently published by the Turkish Ministry of National Education in 2018, was used to determine which learning outcomes are related to tourism and sustainable tourism. Accordingly, a total of 131 learning outcomes were listed: 33 in 4th grade, 33 in 5th grade, 34 in 6th grade, and 31 in 7th grade. In the second phase of the study, a search using the keyword "BlaBlaCar" on the sikayetvar.com website yielded a total of 217 complaints and reviews (the total number available on the website). It was found that all complaints and reviews related to BlaBlaCar were submitted between June 9, 2021, and July 23, 2024.

Data Analysis

In the study, document analysis was conducted to identify the learning outcomes in the social studies curriculum related to tourism and sustainable tourism. The process followed the stages recommended by Altheide and Schneider (2013) for document analysis, which include data collection, coding, analysis, and reporting. In this type of analysis, reliability is established if the same dataset, analyzed under similar conditions, leads other researchers to the same conclusions (Altheide, 1996). To ensure reliability in this study, researcher triangulation was employed, and Miles and Huberman's (1994) reliability formula [$\text{Percent of Agreement} = (\text{Consensus} / (\text{Agreement} + \text{Disagreement})) \times 100$] was used. In this context, to determine which learning outcomes in the social studies curriculum are related to tourism and sustainable tourism, all outcomes were individually reviewed by three researchers specializing in social studies, tourism, and qualitative research. Since full consensus was reached on the outcomes deemed unrelated to tourism and sustainable tourism, the reliability for these outcomes was calculated to be 100%. For the outcomes considered related to tourism and sustainable tourism, the reliability calculations were 95% and 100%, respectively. According to Miles and Huberman (1994), for a study to be considered reliable, all reliability results must exceed 70%. In this study, the fact that all results are above 70% indicates the reliability of the research.

In the second part of the study, which focuses on complaints and reviews related to BlaBlaCar, the netnography method was employed. Since data in netnography typically consist of notes and records from digital environments, content analysis is used in the data analysis phase (Zerenler, 2020). Additionally, descriptive analysis was also utilized in analyzing the data in this study. Content analysis, which is useful

for examining people’s thoughts, beliefs, attitudes, and values (Stemler, 2000), is a process aimed at reducing and interpreting large amounts of qualitative data to identify their meanings and consistencies (Patton, 2014). With this method, the content of the data is examined to identify which thoughts, beliefs, attitudes, and values are emphasized the most and the least. Descriptive analysis, another data analysis technique used in the study, involves presenting the data directly as quotes, without any alterations (Yıldırım & Şimşek 2013). The purpose of this technique is to present different perspectives on the same topic in a clear and systematic manner (Demir, 2009). In this study, both content analysis and descriptive analysis were conducted using the MAXQDA 20 software package. To ensure the reliability of these analyses, the same steps used in evaluating the le-

arning outcomes were followed. Reliability calculations for the two themes identified through content analysis were 97% for the first theme and 100% for the second theme.

Findings

Findings on the Relationship between SSC Outcomes and Tourism and Sustainable Tourism

The SSC includes 27 skills and 18 values (Table 1), along with 131 learning outcomes. It is possible to relate all these skills and values directly or indirectly to tourism. Therefore, while no specific analysis was conducted on these skills and values, they are presented in this section to provide a clear understanding of their scope.

Table 1. Skills and Values in SSC

Skills			Values		
1. Research	12. Communication	22. Problem solving	1. Justice	10. Aesthetics	
2. Environmental literacy	13. Cooperation	23. Social engagement	2. Giving importance to family unity	11. Equality	
3. Perception of change and continuity	14. Recognizing stereotypes and prejudices	24. Drawing and interpreting tables, graphs and diagrams	3. Independence	12. Freedom	
4. Digital literacy	15. Using evidence	25. Using Turkish language correctly, properly and effectively	4. Peace	13. Respect	
5. Critical thinking	16. Decision-making	26. Innovative thinking	5. Scientificity	14. Love	
6. Empathy	17. Location analysis	27. Perception of time and chronology	6. Hard work	15. Responsibility	
7. Financial literacy	18. Media literacy		7. Solidarity	16. Saving	
8. Entrepreneurship	19. Perception of space		8. Sensitivity	17. Patriotism	
9. Observation	20. Self-control		9. Integrity	18. Helpfulness	
10. Map literacy	21. Political literacy				
11. Legal literacy					

The letters and numbers preceding the outcomes in Table 2 correspond to the codes used in the curriculum (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Example of Numbering the Outcomes
Source: Ministry of National Education (2018)

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Regarding the learning outcomes, document analysis revealed that nearly 25% of the 131 outcomes are directly or indirectly related to tourism, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Tourism Related Outcomes in SSC

Grade	Learning Area	Outcome
4	Culture and Heritage	SB.4.2.2. Provides examples by researching the elements reflecting the national culture in his/her family and environment.
	People, Places and Environments	SB.4.3.3. Distinguishes natural and human elements in his/her environment.
	Production, Distribution and Consumption	SB.4.5.4. Creates a sample budget of his/her own.
	Global Connections	SB.4.7.2. Comprehends Türkiye's relations with its neighbors and other Turkish Republics.
	Global Connections	SB.4.7.3. Compares the cultural elements of different countries with the cultural elements of Türkiye.
5	Culture and Heritage	SB.5.2.1. Recognizes the important contributions of Anatolian and Mesopotamian civilizations to human history based on their concrete remains.
	Culture and Heritage	SB.5.2.2. Presents natural assets and historical places, objects and artifacts in his/her environment.
	Culture and Heritage	SB.5.2.3. Compares the cultural characteristics of various parts of our country with the cultural characteristics of the environment in which he/she lives and identifies similar and different elements between them.
	Culture and Heritage	SB.5.2.4. Analyses the role of cultural elements in the coexistence of people.
	Culture and Heritage	SB.5.2.5. Evaluates the historical development of cultural elements in daily life.
	People, Places and Environments	SB.5.3.2. Explains the effects of climate on human activities in his/her environment by giving examples from his/her daily life.
	People, Places and Environments	SB.5.3.3. Provides examples of the effects of natural and human characteristics on population and settlement in and around the place where he/she lives.
	Science, Technology and Society	SB.5.4.1. Discusses the impact of technology use on socialization and social relations.
	Production, Distribution and Consumption	SB.5.5.1. Analyses the economic activities of the place where he/she lives and his/her environment.
	Production, Distribution and Consumption	SB.5.5.2. Recognizes the professions that develop depending on the economic activities in and around the place where he/she lives.
	Production, Distribution and Consumption	SB.5.5.3. Analyses the effects of economic activities in the environment on people's social lives.
	Global Connections	SB.5.7.1. Researches the role of the place where he/she lives and its environment in the economic relations between Türkiye and other countries.
	Global Connections	SB.5.7.2. Discusses the effects of communication and transportation technology on economic relations between countries.
Global Connections	SB.5.7.3. Explains the importance of tourism in international relations.	
Global Connections	SB.5.7.4. Provides examples of common heritage elements found in various countries.	

6	Culture and Heritage	SB.6.2.5. Explains the role of historical trade routes in political, cultural and economic relations between societies.
	People, Places and Environments	SB.6.3.2. Examines the landforms, climate characteristics and vegetation cover of Türkiye's basic physical geography features on the relevant maps.
	People, Places and Environments	SB.6.3.3. Shows the basic human geography features of Türkiye on the relevant maps.
	Science, Technology and Society	SB.6.4.2. Expresses ideas about the effects of scientific and technological developments on future life.
	Production, Distribution and Consumption	SB.6.5.1. Relates the resources and economic activities of our country.
	Production, Distribution and Consumption	SB.6.5.3. Prepares investment and marketing project proposals taking into account the geographical characteristics of Türkiye.
	Global Connections	SB.6.7.1. Analyses Türkiye's cultural, social, political and economic relations with the Turkish Republics and neighboring states.
7	Global Connections	SB.6.7.2. Analyses Türkiye's economic relations with other countries.
	Individual and Society	SB.7.1.2. Uses positive ways of communication in individual and social relations.
	People, Places and Environments	SB.7.3.4. Provides examples of negative situations that may arise in case of restriction of the freedom of settlement and travel among fundamental rights.

According to Table 2, 30 of the 131 outcomes in the spiral-structured SSC were found to be related to tourism. An examination of the distribution of these outcomes across learning areas indicates that the "Global Connections" learning area contains the highest number of tourism-related outcomes, with a total of eight. This is followed by the "Culture and Heritage" learning area with seven outcomes, and the "People, Places, and Environments" and "Production, Distribution, and Consumption" areas, each with six outcomes. The learning area with the fewest tourism-related outcomes (one) was found to

be "Individual and Society." The learning area that does not contain any tourism-related outcomes, and therefore is not included in the table, is "Active Citizenship." The outcomes emphasizing tourism are primarily concentrated in the 5th grade, with a total of 15 outcomes. Outcomes represent the behaviors and/or actions that students are expected to acquire. From this perspective, the sustainability of tourism-related outcomes reflects the sustainability of both society and tourism. The outcomes related to sustainable tourism and the dimensions they are associated with are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Sustainable Tourism Related Outcomes in SSC

Grade	Learning Area	Outcome	Sustainability Dimension
4	Individual and Society	SB.4.1.5. Respects the different characteristics of other individuals.	Social
	Science, Technology and Society	SB.4.4.5. Uses technological products without harming himself/herself, others and nature.	Environmental
	Production, Distribution and Consumption	SB.4.5.2. Recognizes the main economic activities in his/her family and immediate environment.	Economic
	Production, Distribution and Consumption	SB.4.5.5. Uses the resources around him/her without wasting them.	Environmental
	Global Connections	SB.4.7.1. Presents various countries in the world.	Social
	Global Connections	SB.4.7.4. Respects different cultures.	Social

5	Science, Technology and Society	SB.5.4.2. Questions the accuracy and reliability of the information he/she accesses online.	Social/ Economic
	Production, Distribution and Consumption	SB.5.5.6. Exercises his/her rights as a conscious consumer.	Social/ Economic
6	Individual and Society	SB.6.1.2. Analyses the place and role of social, cultural and historical ties in the formation of social unity.	Social
	Individual and Society	SB.6.1.3. Questions prejudices against differences in order to live in harmony in society.	Social
	Individual and Society	SB.6.1.5. Defends that solutions to a problem should be based on rights, responsibilities and freedoms.	Social/ Economic
7	Production, Distribution and Consumption	SB.6.5.2. Analyses the effects of unconscious consumption of resources on living life.	Environmental
	Individual and Society	SB.7.1.1. Analyses attitudes and behaviors that affect communication and questions his/her own attitudes and behaviors.	Social
	Individual and Society	SB.7.1.4. Exercises his/her rights and fulfils his/her responsibilities while using communication tools.	Social
	Global Connections	SB.7.7.3. Questions stereotypes about various cultures.	Social

Upon examining Table 3, it is evident that only 15 of the 131 total outcomes are related to sustainable tourism. Six outcomes are found at the 4th grade level, two at the 5th grade level, four at the 6th grade level, and three at the 7th grade level. Another notable point is that the majority of the outcomes are related to the social dimension of sustainable tourism, while fewer outcomes are associated with the environmental and economic dimensions. Additionally, it was found that three outcomes are related to both the social and economic dimensions. In the environmental dimension, outcomes such as “using technological products without harming nature” and “using resources without wasting” are included. In the economic dimension, outcomes such as “recognizing the main economic activities in their environment” and “exercising rights as a conscious consumer” are emphasized. In the social dimension, key outcomes include “questioning stereotypes” and “examining attitudes and behaviors in communication.”

Findings on the Relationship between the Skills, Values and Outcomes of BlaBlaCar Application Users and the Economic Dimension of Sustainable Tourism

Through the analysis of all reviews related to BlaBlaCar on the Sikayetvar.com website, two main themes were identified: “economic impact on sustainable tourism” and “socio-cultural impact on sustainable tourism.” The first theme, “economic impact on sus-

tainable tourism,” consists of seven sub-themes and nine codes (Figure 2). The numbers in parentheses next to the codes indicate how many users mentioned the respective code. A total of 178 codes makes up Theme 1.

Figure 2. Economic Impact on Sustainable Tourism (Theme 1)

Unfair profit claims, non-payment of fares and driver fraud are factors that affect users economically and contribute to the problem of fraud. Prominent user statements that highlight this issue are as follows: “The trip advertisement says 100 TL, but when I send a message, he asks for five times that amount, 500 TL (P10, P65).” “They have turned the application into a business (P22).” “The purpose of BlaBla’s establishment is not profit. If people are making a profit, it should be taxed (P55).” In addition to passengers’ reviews about being overcharged by drivers, some drivers also made comments indicating that some passengers did not pay the fare. Some of

the complaints regarding this issue are as follows: "The person I picked up said he would pay through IBAN, but when we arrived at the destination, he hurried away without paying (P7)." "A woman got into my car along with two others. When she got off, she said she did not have any money and would transfer it to my IBAN number. She did not transfer my money and said that she would file a complaint against me with the prosecutor's office for bothering her (P198)." On the issue of driver fraud, some users made the following remarks:

"I had to travel from Denizli to Bodrum, this is what happened to me: They want to receive payment via a link by sharing fake trips and the amounts in the links are like 1000 TL, and they keep sending links with reduced amounts until they get it, people who use BlaBlaCar, please let's pay attention to this issue (P205)." "They take people's money and then cancel the trip (P98)."

In addition to the comments made by drivers and passengers about one another, there are also comments regarding the pricing policy of the BlaBlaCar application. BlaBlaCar calculates the maximum amounts that drivers can charge based on the distance travelled. However, many drivers argue that these amounts are significantly lower than the fuel costs they incur and should be updated. Some drivers even suggest that the depreciation of their vehicles should be factored into these fees. In contrast, as indicated by the statements above, passengers do not agree with drivers asking for amounts higher than those set by the application. One user who blames the application for the conflict between passengers and drivers over pricing explains the situation with the following statement: "BlaBlaCar sets its prices based on fuel costs from five years ago, which leads to disputes between vehicle owners and passengers. I believe they do this deliberately and with bad intentions (P16)." A user who uses the service offered by the application but prefers that the application does not interfere with the pricing commented: "They don't know how much fuel costs, and I guess they don't know how much car parts cost. No one has to drive for free. If we can agree on a reasonable price among ourselves, the rest is none of your business (P39)."

A penalty is imposed on the drivers who either demand fares higher than the established rates or use vehicles not suitable for the journey. This penalty is enforced by deactivating the drivers' accounts if complaints are made by passengers about such behavior. The comments from drivers who claim their accounts were unfairly deactivated are as follows: "BlaBlaCar is unfairly closing accounts (P69)." "The account I've been using for 8 years was suspended. When I emailed them, I was told that a passenger claimed I had asked for a different fare, which was given as the reason. This never happened. I think a

passenger said something like that when I did not accept what he wanted (P63)." A driver who objected to the deactivation of his account, despite admitting that he had charged more than the price set by the app, expressed this situation in the following words: "The app sets the price at 200 TL, we tell passengers 500 TL. They complain about us and suspend our account. No one should be sorry about this. There is absolutely no profit being made here. I complain that my account was examined in detail and closed unjustly (P57)."

Although they are few in number, there are also positive comments about the BlaBlaCar application on Sikayetvar.com. These reviews generally focus on the economic aspects of the service: "BlaBlaCar is a big success, especially at this time when fuel prices are rising, as it allows sharing travel costs (K151)." "The main purpose here is to share the trip, and I have no intention of making money (K5)." "Please do not confuse me, and others like me who share rides as per the app's intended purpose, with those using it for commercial gain or only accepting female passengers (K40)."

Since the route prices set by the application are considered low by drivers, they may ask passengers to pay more than the amounts defined by the app, resulting in bargaining between passengers and drivers. This situation is reflected in user reviews as follows:

"Bus tickets to İstanbul currently cost 700 TL. I'm offering 300 TL with my private car, but the offers I receive are around 150 TL, 90 TL. Just getting in and out of a taxi costs 100 TL. Shame on you (K14)." "For someone who thinks it's fair to travel a route where the bus fare is 800 TL for just 300 TL in a private car, they should question why the Turkish Lira has lost value or eat less and buy themselves a car (K56)."

After passengers make their payment for the trip, issues may arise with refunds if the trip is cancelled. Statements of participants on this matter are as follows:

"I sent an offer to a female driver named X, and she accepted. I arrived at the designated meeting point, but shortly before the trip, she told me she wouldn't be taking me on this journey. I had to cancel my trip. However, the refund was not processed to my PayPal account. Could you please refund my money? (K99)." "The refund for my cancelled trip has not been made. It was supposed to be processed within 5 days, but it's been 10 days, and I still haven't received any payment (K58)."

In the trips made through the BlaBlaCar platform, the amount passengers pay to drivers is referred to as a "cost contribution," and this amount is set by the application. The application aims to fairly distribute the travel costs ensuring that drivers do not

make a profit. Even if the driver fills all the seats in their vehicle, they do not make a profit but are only able to cover fuel expenses by requesting the cost contribution set by the platform from the passengers. Seven and Öksüzöğlü (2020) highlight that if a profit is made, the transport contract outlined in Article 850 of the Turkish Commercial Code (TCC) must be taken into consideration. The transport contract, which is required when passengers or goods are carried for a price, is not valid if there is no obligation to pay a transport fare. Therefore, they argue that when the driver does not earn a profit, a transport contract cannot be considered applicable. Whether the trips made through the BlaBlaCar platform fall under the category of "gratuitous transport" or require a transport contract remains a debated issue today. Since a clear legal framework has not been established, drivers and passengers who are subject to traffic inspections during their trip are fined. The following statements from two participants support this:

"I was fined 20,000 liras for unlicensed transportation and my vehicle was blocked for 60 days, even though I met my passengers through the app and stated that no fee was charged. Passengers were also fined 1,300 liras (P53)." "The application is illegal. If detected, high fines are imposed on the passenger and driver (P23)."

Findings on the Relationship between the Skills, Values and Outcomes of BlaBlaCar Application Users and the Social Dimension of Sustainable Tourism

In Theme 2, referred to as the socio-cultural impact of sustainable tourism, six sub-themes are identified: "harassment," "deception," "indifference," "insult," "irresponsibility," and "socialization." The total number of codes contributing to these sub-themes and, consequently, to the main theme is 155 (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Socio-Cultural Impact on Sustainable Tourism (Theme 2)

Within the theme of socio-cultural impact, the sub-theme that received the most comments from users was harassment. There are two situations that contributed to the emergence of the harassment sub-theme: first, male drivers preferring only female

passengers, and second, male drivers harassing the female passengers with whom they share the trip. Some users commented on drivers who only accept female passengers as follows: "[...] He added the phrase 'ladies only' in the description of the ad... (P139)." "[...] Because I am a man, he replies that the vehicle is full. After 15-20 minutes, when my girlfriend next to me asks, he says there is an empty seat (P125)." "[...] We tried it with 6 people, the result was always the same. Some even offered not to charge any fare for my girlfriend (P211)." "Although I don't want to generalize all users, ninety percent of them only accept women (P32)." "Male passengers are not preferred; most members use it for dating purposes (P88)." "[...] The ultimate purpose of the trip is seen as sexual satisfaction (P97)." A driver who admitted that he only accepts female passengers explained the reason for this as follows: "Yes, all of my passengers have been women so far, and I have not charged any of them. The reason I use the application is my panic attack disorder. I cannot travel alone because of this. I would prefer a woman who does not shut up than a male passenger sitting next to me, of course (P154)." Regarding the issue of driver harassment, some of the users stated as follows:

"There are people who use the trip as an excuse to get our phone numbers and make ridiculous offers (P183)." "I was harassed by a man. I reported the member. Nothing has been done, he still continues to advertise. Don't you realize that women who ride in this person's car are at risk? Such situations need to be prevented, I am the victim here (P207)."

Some of the drivers do not respond to passenger messages despite posting a ride, say the vehicle is full when it is empty, cancel rides for no reason, use fake profiles, and make misleading comments about their passengers on the app. Quotes from user comments on driver dishonesty are as follows: "Trips are cancelled arbitrarily. They even advertise with someone else's account (P110)." "[...] There are men who open a female profile (P35)." Two users who stated that the comments made about them were unfair expressed their opinions as follows: "Although I told the BlaBlaCar help service that the comment made about me was false, they did not respond back (P135)." "I want the negative comment to be corrected, otherwise I will take legal action against [BlaBlaCar] (P47)."

It was observed that both the drivers and the passengers criticized one another for insensitivity, with most of these criticisms coming from the passengers. Some important comments made by the passengers who expressed that they felt victimized due to trip cancellations or being left stranded outside the agreed location are as follows: "I received information from the driver before departure and waited at the waiting point, but he did not show up. I was victimized at 10 o'clock at night and could not find another

vehicle. I had no place to stay. I was hung out to dry (K100).” “Everything that was booked was turned upside down. The money we spent on the hotel reservation was wasted (P103).” “My friends who had a shift the next morning could neither arrange a bus ticket nor make it to their shift (P146).” “We could not go to the university for the exam, our semester was extended, and we have suffered financial losses (P167).” “He left me halfway by saying that his route had changed (P15).” Three of the drivers explained their cases of victimization as follows:

“We are victimized because of the actions and behaviors of the passengers. The people we help with peanuts are busy complaining and closing BlaBlaCar accounts when there is empty seat, the distances we travel are not short, we have to choose people, if we accept everyone, what is the difference between us and pirate drivers (P69)?”
“[...] At the same time, sometimes there are people who abuse your property, they wear it out, they can even damage it (P45).”
“I couldn’t turn someone away, I took him with his dog because he was a student, and my car was full of hair (P177).”

In disagreements between drivers and passengers, most of the insults and inappropriate behaviors come from the drivers. Both drivers and passengers commented on this issue as follows: “[...] There are people who get nasty and insult and swear when you say the price is too high (K95).” “When I say I filed a complaint, they say go ahead and complain to whomever you want, I indicated 18 TL as a representative amount (K123).” “[...] He threatened me when I said I would complain about his account (P61).” “It is not right to think that passengers are always right. It is unacceptable for some people to behave like commercial vehicle drivers (P5).” “People ask you to pick them up from a different route or to carry their items (P30).”

Some of the drivers on the platform who advertise ridesharing use company-owned vehicles or their freight vehicles instead of their personal cars. Therefore, passengers also stated that these vehicles are not suitable for travelling: “The driver picks up passengers without the company’s approval. His vehicle is a long truck (P13).” “The model of the vehicle to be travelled was not mentioned and there was no information about that. The vehicle belonged to a cargo company and was a lorry (P176).” One passenger’s comment on another irresponsible behavior, the driver’s use of banned substances during the travel, is as follows: “Person X smoked weed in the car. I will file a complaint. Those who developed this application have not taken my complaint into consideration yet (P15)!”

The purpose of the application is to benefit people economically, socially and environmentally by providing a platform for shared travel. Upon analyzing

user comments, it is evident that they mostly focus on the economic aspect of the application. Although the number of comments on social experiences come second to economic comments, there is only one positive review on this subject: “[...] You also meet new people and gain experience. A human experience (P45).”

Discussion

The social studies course plays a significant role in values education by aiming to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and values essential for participating in societal life. According to the findings, the values embraced by society and expressed in the social studies curriculum have deteriorated. This raises questions regarding the true reach and effectiveness of value education in social studies. Another key objective of the social studies course is to familiarize students with tourism, elucidate its significance, and cultivate awareness of its fundamental components (Yıldırım & Çetin, 2022). An analysis of the findings presented in Table 1 reveals that the skills and values included in the curriculum contribute to the development of tourism awareness in individuals. Similarly, the program outcomes presented in Table 2 support individuals’ development in technological, socio-cultural, environmental, and economic fields, which may relate to tourism. However, the findings indicate a potential disconnect between the theoretical topics outlined in the curriculum to develop tourism awareness and the challenges faced during implementation.

There are potential consequences of the inadequacies in the skills, values, and outcomes that are theoretically claimed to be transferred into practice, particularly in terms of the dimensions of sustainable development. For instance, fraudulent activities stemming from behaviors such as deceit, corruption, and false statements can cause significant damage to businesses. According to a report prepared by the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners, businesses in the United States lost 2 million dollars in 2006 alone due to fraudulent misrepresentation (Krippel et al., 2008). In addition to the direct economic impacts caused by fraudulent activities, businesses may also incur indirect economic losses due to the resulting negative image. Indeed, image plays a crucial role in guiding individuals’ decision-making processes when selecting a destination and serves as a distinguishing factor among competing destinations (Phau, Shanka & Dhayan, 2010). The findings reveal that fraudulent activities originating from both drivers and passengers contribute to a negative image as well as various economic losses. Such incidents, which undermine society’s sense of security, can render tourism activities economically unsustainable. This view is supported by the fact that visitors tend to choose travel destinations based on

their personal perceptions of safety and security (Pizam, 1982).

Correctly establishing the pricing policy for services is one of the key elements that ensures the economic sustainability of tourism activities. Forbes et al. (2014) stated that poor pricing policies can lead to a decline in tourism activities, causing developing countries to lose the economic benefits they might otherwise gain from tourism. The findings of this study indicate that the pricing policy of the travel application in question has not been appropriately defined for passengers or drivers. As noted by participants, the erroneous implementation of the pricing policy may be attributed to the neglect of the primary cost factor: fuel price. Moreover, flaws in the pricing policy can lead drivers and passengers to negotiate and agree on a new price through bargaining. The prices determined through this method often become a new source of conflict between the parties, leaving both sides dissatisfied with the transaction. Findings related to behaviors stemming from both the flawed pricing policy and the bargaining process indicate that travel activities in Türkiye are not economically sustainable.

Rights and regulations play a crucial role in shaping travel and tourism opportunities. The impact of these rights and regulations has the power to both increase and restrict travel mobility (Coles & Hall, 2011). Such regulations are implemented to promote tourism products in both domestic and international markets, engage with national and international organizations and create favorable conditions for the development of the tourism industry (Safaeva et al., 2019). However, the findings suggest that the favorable conditions expected from the implementation of rights and regulations have not been realized. Specifically, with regard to the requirement for transport permits, account closures, and refund conditions, the legal and technical foundations of the travel application's terms of use are found to be inadequate and ambiguous. The occurrence of unethical offers by the parties and the resulting conflicts can be attributed to the inadequacy of the travel application's terms of use. Such issues related to travel activities could result in significant damage to the tourism industry, which is one of the main sectors it represents. The tourism industry, comprising various sectors, plays a crucial role in economic, political, and socio-cultural dimensions of every country (Safaeva et al., 2019). Therefore, to enhance the effectiveness of services in tourism, it is essential to implement comprehensive legal regulations aimed at addressing sector-specific problems (Dmitrieva et al., 2020).

The sharing economy is a socio-economic model based on renting, sharing, and borrowing, developed as a response to the concept of overconsumption. It is widely recognized in the transportation sector

through applications like Uber and BlaBlaCar (Curtis & Mont, 2020). The main objective of the BlaBlaCar application is to share costs, such as fuel and road expenses, entirely within the framework of the sharing economy, without any profit-oriented exchange of services (BlaBlaCar, 2024). The findings, based on a few positive reviews, indicate that although inefficient, some economic benefit can still be derived from the service exchange offered by the application. The inefficiency of the transportation service offered by the application can be attributed to the aforementioned regulatory inadequacies, which render the service economically unsustainable. Addressing these issues through targeted actions could, in fact, render the application far more efficient in economic terms. By allowing individuals to fill the empty seats in their vehicles, the application offers an ecological and economic solution to the growing number of vehicles in the transportation system (Cohen & Kietzmann, 2014). In this context, when the overall conflicts between parties are considered, the travel application has not fully achieved its economic objectives.

Negative interactions lead to a decline in overall travel quality (Korzay & Alvarez, 2005), and one of the negative behaviors is harassment, where tourists feel uncomfortable or threatened (Alrawadieha et al., 2019). The findings show that harassment is the most significant negative behavior within socio-cultural factors. Similarly, other research has shown that another prominent sharing economy application, Uber, faced serious issues due to harassment allegations made by a former employee (Clark & Myers, 2018). The cases identified in the study, which can result in substantial economic losses and severely undermine trust-based interpersonal relationships, can be attributed to the use of travel applications for reasons other than their intended function. Indeed, Alrawadieha et al. (2019) found that harassment has several detrimental outcomes, including reduced satisfaction, a decline in experience quality, and a negative impact on the intention to recommend.

Several uncertainties are introduced with ride-sharing-based travel, including the distrust caused by fake profiles, uncertainty about whether traffic rules will be followed, the potential for substance abuse, and the possibility of traveling in poorly maintained, uncomfortable, and unsafe vehicles (Paul, 2023). These uncertainties are consistent with the findings of the current study. As shown in Figure 3, passenger and driver complaints revolve around behaviors that foster insecurity and uncertainty, such as creating fake profiles, unjustified trip cancellations, misleading reviews, insults stemming from unfair criticism, traveling in inappropriate vehicles, and the use of banned substances. These behaviors, which highlight the unsustainability of social relations from a socio-cultural perspective, are driving people—especially women and the elderly—away from ride-sharing,

as noted in Loukaitou-Sideris' (2014) study.

The weakening of social connections (Parigi & State, 2014), along with negative social impacts such as safety concerns and class divisions (Edelman, Luca, & Svirsky, 2017), can emerge as significant downsides of travel applications. However, these platforms can also offer social benefits, such as opportunities for drivers and passengers to get to know one another and form new friendships (Fitzmaurice et al., 2020). Among the findings, only one user comment reflects this positive outcome. Given the overall nature of relationships developed through the travel application, it would be misleading to conclude that human relations are socio-culturally healthy based solely on this single positive behavior.

Conclusion and Implications

The social studies course has multifaceted objectives, including teaching individuals their basic rights, helping them discover their talents, instilling values as part of society, promoting respect for human rights, and teaching them to protect their own rights (Tonga, 2022). In line with these objectives and in response to the evolving and changing structure of society, the social studies course encompasses a wide range of topics, concepts, and fields (İlhan, Şeker, & Kapıcı, 2015). Tourism is one of the concepts taught to students in the SSC due to its significant contribution to the economic and socio-cultural development of countries (Kaya, 2019). Additionally, tourism has a long-standing connection with sustainability, as it is one of the first industries to define principles and action plans aimed at implementing sustainable tourism (Budeanu et al., 2016). In this context, the aim of this study is to determine to what extent the desired outcomes have been achieved through social studies education, which aims to impart the skills and values necessary for sustainable tourism. However, the data obtained in the study did not reveal any findings related to the environmental dimension of sustainability. Therefore, the study focuses on the social and economic dimensions of sustainability.

This study is considered important because it reveals the extent to which individuals possess the skills, values, and outcomes necessary for the social and economic aspects of sustainability and evaluates the adequacy of the social studies curriculum in addressing related issues. Identifying the shortcomings of the social studies program in instilling the intended outcomes will provide valuable insights for practitioners, both theoretically and practically, on the steps needed to address these gaps. In this context, the recommendations made in the study to address existing deficiencies are expected to contribute to societal well-being. Additionally, the periodic revisions of the social studies curriculum and the continued implementation of action plans related to

sustainability underscore the study's relevance and timeliness.

In this study, the BlaBlaCar travel application has served as a litmus test, highlighting societal trends, both positive and negative. The archival findings indicate that all the values and skills included in the social studies program contribute to a deeper understanding of sustainability in tourism. Similarly, nearly one-third of the program's outcomes are shown to support the development of tourism and the concept of sustainability within tourism. However, the findings from the field indicate that all these elements, which are conveyed theoretically in the curriculum, cannot be sufficiently reflected in practice. Moreover, individual behaviors have created negative effects both economically and socio-culturally. Among these negative impacts, the economic domain accounts for 53.4%, while the socio-cultural domain represents 46.6%. This result highlights that when addressing the shortcomings of the social studies curriculum, equal importance should be given to both areas in a balanced manner. The study reveals significant implications for eliminating these deficiencies through the balanced policies it proposes.

Theoretical and Practical Implications

Findings indicate that the values embraced by society and expressed in the social studies curriculum have deteriorated. Redesigning educational programs can be prioritized to prevent the deterioration of values. As Deveci & Selanik-Ay (2009) stated, programs with planned activities can incorporate education with the appropriate content to help students acquire these values, and school-family collaboration can also be crucial in this regard. Additionally, informational seminars on values education could be offered to families. Furthermore, in-service training could be provided to social studies teachers, enabling them to design a more structured, real-life, activity-based teaching process for values education. The fact that students with different cultural characteristics are in the same class can also make the implementation of SSC difficult. As Dack and Triplett (2020) stated, teachers can adjust their teaching strategies to modify the social studies course to accommodate these differences. In addition to values, skills and outcomes are fundamental topics that should be emphasized not only in social studies but also in tourism education. A tourism-themed learning area could be created within the SSC, where knowledge, skills, and values related to tourism awareness could be incorporated into the program.

Research findings show that the skills, values, and outcomes theoretically conveyed in the curriculum are not sufficiently reflected in practice. Building on this, in social studies courses, the effects of negative behaviors such as harassment, dishonesty, and insult could be taught to students in a realistic manner

through workshops, drama methods, metaverse, or virtual reality applications. In other words, innovative methods could be employed to focus on value-based education when teaching tourism-related outcomes in the social studies curriculum, providing students with practical, immersive learning experiences that mirror real-world situations. Through these experiences, the theoretically conveyed information can become more lasting, helping shape the desired behaviors in individuals. As societies transition from traditional to modern structures, changes in the socio-cultural and demographic characteristics of developing countries lead to significant changes in their social structures (Kızmaz, 2012). The study's negative effects could stem from the lack of a social studies curriculum that adapts to Türkiye's evolving development. To address this issue, the social studies curriculum implemented by a developed European country with similar cultural characteristics during its developmental period could be studied for reference. Additionally, users seem to exploit the flexibility of the BlaBlaCar app features, leading to negative sociocultural and economic impacts. A study to identify the features that can make the application more restrictive in order to prevent such negative effects would also make a significant contribution to the field.

This study shows that individual behaviors that do not align with the principles of sustainability in tourism have the greatest impact on the economic and socio-cultural domains. It appears that addressing behaviors that negatively affect sustainability principles in the economic domain is relatively easier. The negative attitudes regarding this area can be explained primarily by policy gaps and legal deficiencies. By implementing appropriate legal measures and introducing new regulations, the negative economic impacts can be mitigated. For example, as seen in the more formal and regulated Uber platform, users' identity information, demographic details, and the technical and maintenance status of vehicles could be verified for accuracy by making the sharing of this information mandatory. This approach could prevent negative behaviors arising from distrust and uncertainty between parties, leading to more efficient economic outcomes.

The identified negative economic impacts related to the understanding of sustainability in tourism are, in order of significance, fraud, incorrect pricing policies, and legal gaps. In contrast, the negative socio-cultural impacts are predominantly caused by harassment, followed by behaviors such as dishonesty and actions that create distrust. It can be argued that the negative economic impacts can be reversed in the short to medium term through the implementation of correct policies and legal regulations. However, as Kristiana et al. (2024) also note, it is important to remember that societal values and cultural practices require long-term and gradual

changes. For this reason, it is crucial for countries to make educational arrangements that will create permanent effects, especially on socio-cultural values.

The research findings have shown that the BlaBlaCar application has serious negative effects, both socio-culturally and economically. Over time, this may lead to the abandonment of such technological applications in favor of traditional means of transportation. This could very likely pose a significant obstacle to the development of technology-based initiatives in that country. As Wang & Chien (2007) stated, the elimination of negative socio-cultural and economic effects will enable the development of such initiatives in the country, given the significant role technology plays in national development.

Limitations and Directions for Future Research

Although this study provides guidance to practitioners in the field from both an economic and socio-cultural perspective, it also has some limitations. This research has bridged two distinct but interconnected fields—social studies and tourism. It also sought to highlight the relationship between social studies education and sustainable tourism. However, as previously mentioned, the data for this study were obtained from a complaint website, meaning that nearly all the feedback was negative. Future research could broaden the scope to include positive feedback when available. Expanding the study to other countries where the BlaBlaCar application is used could also provide more comprehensive insights into the effects of sustainability. Additionally, analyzing other platforms as part of the sample could allow for comparative evaluations, enabling researchers to identify the most effective features for preserving values. Moreover, exploring the sustainability of tourism within different sectors other than transportation—such as food and beverage, accommodation, and recreation businesses—would diversify the understanding of sustainable practices. By doing so, integrating findings from various platforms and sectors could contribute to a more holistic view of sustainability in tourism. Thus, the social studies curriculum's role in addressing areas relevant to the public good could be further clarified and made more explicit.

Disclosure Statements

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